

MODERN PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES TO THE MODERNIZATION OF ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical-methodological foundations of the formation of eco-literacy in students in the process of modernization of environmental education, pedagogical-psychological features of modernization of environmental education, the corrective effect of eco-creativity, eco-responsibility, eco-literacy competencies in students between nature and human relations studied. Modern pedagogical approaches to the modernization of environmental education are also analyzed.

Key words: ecology, biosphere, formation of eco-literacy, environment, national values, healthy lifestyle, ecological dialogue, pedagogical process, professional-pedagogical activity, integrative, value, value approach, national, historical, technological.

INTRODUCTION. In the world, the deepening of anthropotechnogenic influence of man on nature, the development of society based on science and innovative technologies is developing an eco-aesthetic attitude to nature. The formation of environmental eco-aesthetics, the expansion of eco-tourism infrastructure and the increase in the types of services in the field indicate that a new approach to nature is being formed in man. In particular, the elimination of global environmental problems recognized by the United Nations requires the active cooperation of the peoples of the world, regardless of their ethno-demographic structure and confessional affiliation, political system and level of economic development, ideological outlook and natural-geographical location, and the formation of a eudomonistic attitude to nature. is putting on the agenda. In this regard, UN Secretary General Antonio Guterres said that the world should stop the "war against nature" and find more political will to fight climate change.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Pedagogical foundations of ecological education are expressed in the research works of Academician I.D. Zverev, A.N. Zakhlebniy, the content, methodology, form, and tools of ecological education in teaching natural sciences by E.O. Turdigulov. The biological direction of ecological education was studied by I. T. Suravegina, as well as socio-philosophical aspects by Y. Shodimetov, B. Ziyomukhamedov. In the researches of L.T.Shonosirova, G.O.Komilova, environmental education of preschool children, and in the researches of M.A.Yuldashev, M.M.Abdullayeva,

M.B.Rahimkulova, G.Sultonova, N.Ashurova, issues of environmental knowledge in primary education were studied.

Abroad, scientists R.G. Barker, W.R. Catton, D.D. Chiras, R.E. Dunlap, the content and essence, structure of environmental education; the issues of creating eco-literacy in students were mentioned in the scientific research of D.H. Meadows, D. L. Meadows, J. Randers, A. W. Wiecker, Ch. M. Geesteranus, J. C. Smith, L. F. Schmore, A. J. Suvan, O. D. Duncan, S. Foresman, and U. Halbach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. To contribute to the elimination of problems related to ecology based on the territorial-geographical, ethnographic-mental characteristics of the regions of the learners in our republic, to increase the ecological literacy of the growing young generation, to form ecological consciousness and ecological culture, and the goal was to effectively organize the process of development, environmental education and upbringing. Based on this goal, the adoption of the concept of development of environmental education in the Republic of Uzbekistan was also an important reality.

In our country, the teaching of ecology today, like the science of philosophy, is formed on the basis of all subjects, so the teacher conducting the lessons should find and apply the social-pedagogical, territorial-geographical, ethnographic-mental aspects of the topics related to nature. , because man always lives in nature and can never leave nature. In fact, man needs nature, in nature man is formed as a simple living organism.

"Natural science" lessons are the main subject of education in primary grades in providing the first ideas about ecology. This educational subject will be very important in the formation of ecological knowledge and concepts. It is extremely important to organize classes in non-traditional ways in order to familiarize students with nature and regularly inform them about various environmental events. Teaching environmental concepts in primary classes is different in that environmental education for primary school students is carried out on the basis of interdisciplinary integration. The purpose of this is to learn about nature and to teach to preserve it, to form interdisciplinary theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications related to ecological education.

In general secondary education, it is integrated into subjects such as Biology, Geography, History, Natural Science. Environmental education is not fully introduced in secondary special vocational education and is mostly conducted by teachers of related subjects due to the small number of hours. A similar situation is observed in higher education. As a result, environmental education, that is, personnel training, is carried out in a way that does not rely

on the competence of students. By 2021, non-ecological subjects would make up 70-75% of the curriculum of "Ecology and environmental protection" education.

In the process of improving the qualifications of personnel and their retraining, the model of the formation of professional competences of ecologists - the interdependence of the components of environmental education - shows the relevance of research. This is related to the specific characteristics of the professional activity of environmental specialists and social demand. For example, the main feature of the model created for the formation of professional competencies of technical-ecologists is the integration of these components, which enhances the formation of comprehensively oriented specialists in the educational process.

As a result, first of all, it means that environmental education is one of the main factors of the development of society. Ecological education is aimed at changing people's attitude towards nature, formation of behavioral and environmental stereotypes, economic and social development, acceptance of new principles of professional ethics by each state and person, culture and justice, some limitations and aimed at the establishment of prohibitions, the development of ecosphere laws;

Secondly, this situation determines the formation of pedagogical conditions for the professional competence of an ecologist;

Thirdly, the technological algorithm of the structure of the environmental education model will be the introduction of environmental education in the future;

Fourthly, it directs environmental education to meet world standards and classifies ecologists to connect this process with production, organizational-management and information-analytical activities;

Fifth, the introduction of new information technologies shows the rapid adaptability of environmental education;

Sixth, along with science, it also develops ecological culture. These, in turn, arise from life experiences and approach moral principles.

The approach based on moral principles is mainly used in folk pedagogy: explanation, example, habituation (learning, training), begging, expressing wishes, begging, giving advice, approving, thanking, although there are methods of praying, forcing, reprimanding, putting, threatening, apologizing, cursing, beating, mainly in the environmental education of students: advice, example (example) it has been confirmed in the experience that the use of methods such as showing, approving and praising, praising, rewarding, prohibiting, and

encouraging gives good results. Experience has shown that teaching and advice are one of the most widely used methods of environmental education of students in folklore.

The stimulation method is one of the most widely used methods of moral education, and it is used in various forms in folklore. They can be interpreted conditionally by dividing them into the following two groups: Approval and praise. In the works of folk art, children's exemplary work for humanity is depicted together with the approval, awarding, thanking and praise of adults. Applause. Alkash is one of the forms of encouragement that has been going on among our people since ancient times. Applause and cursing were used in the interaction of certain social groups and individuals, in expressing gratitude or malice and displeasure in relation to each other's positive or negative behavior.

CONCLUSION. It is of great importance to widely introduce the principles of environmental education at all stages of continuous education, to increase the environmental knowledge of young people, and in particular, to form knowledge and skills in the field of environmental protection in the higher education system. It is desirable to demonstrate to students the concepts of preserving flora and fauna, and strengthening the sense of caring for them through videos and documentaries. The impact of the full understanding and knowledge of environmental problems and nature conservation on students should be based on the principle of instruction.

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